
GRAM PANCHAYAT SELF-FUNDING REVENUE ANALYSIS - A STUDY**Ronak M. Dhimmarr***M.Com, B.Ed.,NET,GSET*

Abstract :

Local self-government organizations include Gram Panchayat, Taluka Panchayat, District Panchayat, Municipality, Municipal Corporation etc. India is a country made up of villages. The development of the rural area is an important factor affecting the Indian economy. An important unit working at the village level is the Gram Panchayat. Gram Panchayat is an independent working organization of local self-government. The Gram Panchayat receives income mainly in two ways. (3) Income of self-funding (3) Income of grant. At the village level, the Gram Panchayat receives income through various types of taxes and taxes. This income is called self-funded income. In this research the income of the self-funded Gram Panchayat is analyzed. In which all aspects related to self-funded income are outlined. It is therefore useful to improve the revenue of the Gram Panchayat. This research is useful not only at the state level but also at the national level. The business of the research presented is the gram panchayat of Valsad district. About 50 gram panchayats have been selected from Valsad, Dharampur, Kaprada, Pardi and Umargam talukas of Valsad district. As well as from which resources the self-funded income of this Gram Panchayat is obtained. They have been analyzed.

1. Introduction

At the grassroots level, the country has special responsibilities and expectations of the Gram Panchayats. Gram Panchayats are the basic unit in the Panchayati Raj structure. Therefore, the building as strong and rich as gram panchayats will be as strong as Panchayati Raj. At the village level, many things are associated with the gram panchayat. It is also necessary to maintain a harmonious coordination with all the things that the Gram Panchayat is involved with such as infrastructure, education, health, housing, water, questions of villagers, schemes etc. That is why it is necessary for the Gram Panchayat to act wisely and carefully for all these things. And the financial convenience for each of these tasks should be in proportion to the need. Therefore, the analysis of the self-funding of the Gram Panchayat is necessary here.

2. Problem statement and definition of words

The title of the problem chosen by the researcher is as follows.

"Gram Panchayat Self-Funding Revenue Analysis: - A Study"

Here are the definitions of important terminology under the heading of research presented.

Gram Panchayat

Gram Panchayat is a local self-government organization working in rural areas.

Self-funded income

Self-funded income means income derived from owning income instruments. The income earned by the various taxes at the village level is the income of the self-funded Gram Panchayat.

3. Research objectives

The research presented was conducted with the following objectives in mind.

- (1) To know about the means for earning revenue of Gram Panchayat.
- (2) To analyze the arrival of self-funding of Gram Panchayat.
- (3) To know what taxes are taken at the village level.
- (4) To know how to increase the revenue of Gram Panchayat Self-Fund.
- (5) To analyze the economic situation of Gram Panchayats.

4. Research questions

The research presented was conducted with the following questions in mind.

- (1) What are the resources for earning revenue of Gram Panchayat?
- (2) What is the revenue of the Gram Panchayat?
- (3) What taxes are taken at the grassroots level?
- (4) How can the self-funded income of the Gram Panchayat be increased?
- (5) How is the economic situation of Gram Panchayats?

5. The importance of research

Every research is useful because "Necessity is the mother of Invention." So every explorer has a basic need that matters. The research presented is about the analysis of the revenue of the Gram Panchayat. So it matters a lot. India is a country made up of villages. There are more than six lakh villages. That is why if the country is to be developed then the villages must be developed. It is important to know what the revenue of the Gram Panchayat funds is, what its resources are, what resources can be used to increase the income of the Gram Panchayat. So, the focus of this research is to increase the financial capacity of the Gram Panchayat ie improve the self-funded income of the Gram Panchayat. This study is useful for the employees, officers, organizations and various departments of the government concerned with the gram panchayats. Also, since this research is directly related to Gram Panchayats, it is useful to strengthen the structure of Panchayati Raj in the country at the national level.

In addition, the importance of the research presented can be as follows:

- (1) The sources of income for self-funded income of the Gram Panchayat will be found.
- (2) An analysis of the income of the self-funded Gram Panchayat will be obtained.
- (3) Information on local taxes taken in the rural area will be obtained.
- (4) There will be ways to increase the self-funded income of the Gram Panchayat.
- (5) An analysis of the economic situation of the Gram Panchayats will be obtained.

6. Information collection

The research presented is based on secondary data. This secondary information includes the circulars of the government, the annual balance of the Gram Panchayat, the Panchayat Act etc.

Demarcation of research

The Demarcation of the research presented are as follows:

- (1) The annual research of the Gram Panchayats has been used as a tool of information in the research presented.
- (2) The research presented includes only gram panchayats of Valsad district as a model. Other Gram Panchayats are not included.
- (3) The sample of research presented includes the gram panchayats of 5 gram panchayats of five talukas of Valsad district in the year 1-5.
- (4) Used secondary information in the research presented.

7. Area and Sample

The area of the research presented was the village panchayat of Valsad district. About 50 gram panchayats have been selected from Valsad, Pardi, Umargam, Dharampur and Kaprada talukas of Valsad district. The head sample was randomly selected.

8. Research findings

The research work presented revealed that the Gram Panchayat uses various tools for earning funds. These include housing taxes, light taxes, cleaning taxes, water taxes, business taxes, market taxes, exemption fees, copy fees, tower rent / tax, mill taxes, license fees, ponds rent etc.

In addition, the findings of the research presented can be as follows:

- (1) The revenue of the village panchayats of the various talukas of Valsad district was not sufficient.
- (2) Information on the means of earning income of the self-funded Gram Panchayat was obtained.
- (3) Information was obtained on various tools for raising the revenue of the Gram Panchayat.
- (4) The economic status of the Gram Panchayats was informed.
- (5) In the remote areas of Kaprada and Dharampur talukas of Valsad district, the self-funded income of the villages was very low which was reported.
- (6) The revenue of the Gram Panchayats near the urban area was relatively high.
- (7) As well as Gram Panchayats in the GIDC area also have a good income.
- (8) The household income of the gram panchayats showed a considerable difference between the various gram panchayats.
- (9) In some Gram Panchayats, the income of the house was reduced due to non-assessment of the property.
- (10) The business tax revenue of the Gram Panchayats with business area was very high.
- (11) In most Gram Panchayats, households and cleanliness are mainly found in self-financing income instruments. Still normal water taxes as well as light taxes are not seen.

● Reference

- (1) Desai K.G. And Desai H.G. (2002), 'Research Practices and Methods'. Ahmedabad : University Book Production Board.
- (2) Annual Terij(2018-19) of the village gram panchayats of different talukas of Valsad district.
- (3) News paper
- (4) Government circulars
- (5) Panchayat Act-1993
- (6) Aggrawal, J.C. (1991). Research and introduction. New Delhi : Arya book depot.